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To cite this article: Carlo Cazzaniga *et al* 2025 *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **3130** 012001

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Application of a 7CLYC scintillator to fast neutron measurements

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Abstract. 7CLYC scintillators have shown excellent performances for fast neutron spectroscopy, thanks to good energy resolution and superb pulse shape discrimination. In this work, a 7CLYC detector has been studied and characterised with monoenergetic neutrons at metrology laboratories. Results of application in a more complex neutron field are presented and discussed.

1. Introduction

The field of neutron detection has witnessed significant advancements with the development of CLYC scintillators ($\text{Cs}_2\text{LiYCl}_6:\text{Ce}$), which comes in the forms of 6CLYC or 7CLYC [1], each tailored to specific neutron energy ranges. 6CLYC scintillators are effective for thermal neutron detection, being enriched with ^6Li that has a very high cross section for the (n,α) reaction [2]. In contrast, the 7CLYC scintillator, enriched with ^7Li , emerges as a promising candidate for fast neutron measurements [3], a domain critical for various scientific and industrial applications. The absence of ^6Li in 7CLYC, that would be present in the natural lithium, is important to minimise the sensitivity of the detector to thermal neutrons. The most interesting reaction in CLYC for fast neutron spectroscopy is the $^{35}\text{Cl}(n, p)^{35}\text{S}$, which has only charged products and gives rise of a full-energy peak, where the whole energy of the neutron is deposited with the addition of a positive Q value of 615 keV. The presence of a full-energy peak is not common in neutron detectors, and it is particularly interesting for neutrons in the range 1 MeV to 4 MeV, as it can be used for high-resolution neutron spectroscopy. It has to be noted that there is an interest for fusion applications for measuring 2.5 MeV neutrons from Deuterium-Deuterium reactions. In this case the $^{35}\text{Cl}(n, p)$ peak in high resolution scintillators can be used for 2.5 MeV neutrons in a similar way for spectroscopy as the $^{12}\text{C}(n,\alpha)$ peak is used in diamond detectors for 14 MeV neutrons (from Deuterium-Tritium reactions). A key feature of the 7CLYC scintillator is its exceptional neutron/gamma discrimination ability [4], achieved through the pulse shape discrimination (PSD) technique.

The current study focuses on the application of a 7CLYC scintillator at the ISIS neutron source at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (UK), where fast neutrons are particularly relevant for the irradiation of microelectronics in the NILE and ChipIR beamlines. The newly established NILE [5], in particular, with its capability to generate monoenergetic 2.5 MeV neutrons from Deuterium-Deuterium reactions, offers an ideal setting for the application of this scintillator.

2. Experimental

2.1 Experimental Setup

A 7CLYC scintillator of 1 inch diameter x 1 inch height by Scionix is coupled to a 51 mm PMT. Negative High Voltage in the range 700-1000V is applied and the signal output is fed directly to a digitizer. Two digitizers with fast sampling rate have been tested in this work: CAEN-DT5751 (10-bit ADC, 1GHz sampling frequency) or CAEN-DT5730S (14-bit, 500MHz), one has higher sampling frequency but lower resolution, and vice versa. The digitizers converted the analog waveforms into binary data and transferred the data to the computer's disk via USB link for offline analysis. Python software was developed to perform data analysis of the scintillator pulses. The pulse processing logic of the code is illustrated in Ref. [6]. PSD is achieved by comparing the charge collected in the early part of the pulse (short gate) Q_s to the long charge (long gate) Q_l . This method is known as the charge comparison method [33] and it is implemented by numerically integrating the pulse twice with respect to a baseline over the short gate and long gate (see FIG. 2.2). The baseline is defined as the average of the first 16 samples of the pulse. A value called the PSD value, which represents information on the pulse shape, is then computed by $PSD = 1 - \frac{Q_s}{Q_l}$.

The optimal value of the long gate does not necessarily cover the entire pulse. Therefore, the

Figure 1. Scatter plot of Pulse Shape Discrimination (PSD) versus Pulse Height (PH) for 7CLYC scintillators exposed to Am-Be neutrons at RAL. Within the neutron counts (n), there is a measurable separation between proton output channel ($^{35}\text{Cl}(n,p)$) and alpha output channel ($^{35}\text{Cl}(n,\alpha)$).

parameter called *integration time* is selected to obtain the best energy resolution without extending the dead-time unnecessarily. The Pulse Height Spectra (PHS) is calibrated using known gamma laboratory sources. Radionuclides used are Na-22, Cs-137, and Bi-207. The gamma energies of these sources are: 0.511 MeV and 1.274 MeV for Na-22, 0.662 MeV for Cs-137, and 0.570 MeV, 1.064 MeV, and 1.770 MeV for Bi-207. In this way, the pulse height, which represents the amount of scintillation light produced for scintillator detectors, is measured in megaelectron-volt electron-equivalent (MeVee). By definition, 1 MeV electrons induce 1 MeVee of scintillation light.

2.2 Optimization of parameters using an AmBe source

The neutron-gamma discrimination performance is quantified by the Figure Of Merit (FOM) value of the PSD spectrum of events within a narrow cut of the PHS [33]. $FOM = d/(\sigma_n + \sigma_\gamma)$,

where d is the separation of the peaks, and σ_n, σ_γ are the full-width-at-half-maximums (FWHM) of the neutron, gamma peaks. The peaks' locations and FWHMs were estimated by double Gaussian peak fitting. The FOM values of the detectors were optimized using the mixed gamma and neutron flux of an Americium-Beryllium (AmBe) source encased in a polyethylene box at RAL. Figure 1 shows a measurement where counts are plotted in a scatterplot of PSD vs Pulse Height. Here one can notice the superb neutron gamma discrimination of 7CLYC. Also, looking at the neutron counts, there is a measurable separation between proton output channel and alpha output channels. The analysis has been repeated scanning values of Q_s and Q_i . After the optimization, the following values have been found to be the best parameters: $Q_s = 100$ ns, and $Q_i = 400$ ns, *Integration Time* = 4500 ns. Measurements with the DT5751 digitizers have been found to be marginally better than the DT5730S, with $FOM = 3.66$ and $FOM = 3.29$ respectively.

Figure 2. Scatter plots of Pulse Shape Discrimination (PSD) versus Pulse Height (PH) for 7CLYC scintillators exposed to fast neutrons and gamma rays at neutron energies of 1.59 MeV, 2.5 MeV, and 4 MeV at PTB.

3. Characterization measurements at Metrology laboratories

3.1 Response to monoenergetic neutrons

The PTB in Braunschweig (Germany) and NPL in Teddington (UK) are neutron metrology laboratories specialised in the production of well-characterised neutron fields in a low-scattering hall. They are dedicated to accurate calibration of neutron measuring devices against international metrology standards, as well as the measurement of the cross-sections of nuclear reactions. Here we tested the 7-CLYC at 13 neutron energies from 1.5 MeV to 14.8 MeV. Discrete neutron energies have been reached by using the reactions ${}^3\text{H}(p,n){}^3\text{He}$, ${}^2\text{H}(d,n){}^3\text{He}$ and ${}^3\text{H}(d,n){}^4\text{He}$ and utilizing the kinematics by placing the detector at different angles with respect to the charged particle beam direction. While the design of the hall greatly reduces background neutrons that are scattering from the walls, floor, and ceiling, the back-scattered neutron background can be measured for later subtraction by using shadow cones provided by PTB and NPL.

Figure 2 presents selected results of scatter plots of Pulse Shape Discrimination (PSD) versus Pulse Height (PH) for neutron energies of 1.59 MeV, 2.5 MeV, and 4 MeV. The x-axis represents the Pulse Height measured in MeV electron-equivalent (MeVee), while the y-axis represents the PSD value. Each plot shows two distinct clusters: gamma rays, which cluster around lower PSD values (approximately 0.60), and fast neutrons, which cluster around higher PSD values (around 0.70-

0.75). The separation between gamma and neutron events is clear across all energy levels, showcasing the scintillator's ability to effectively differentiate between these interactions. The full-energy peak due to the $^{35}\text{Cl}(n, p)^{35}\text{S}$ reaction is clearly visible in the distinctive feature of a high-intensity spot well-separated from other events. The position of the peak is clearly shifting with neutron energy (plus Q value). At 4 MeV one can notice a new high-intensity spot appearing on the left. This is due to the proton emission channel $^{35}\text{Cl}(n, p_1)$ to the first excited state of ^{35}S now being open. This feature does not compromise the integrity of the full-energy peak, therefore high-resolution spectroscopy is still possible at this energy.

Figure 3 presents the neutron response spectra of the 7CLYC scintillator for various neutron energies. Panel (a) shows the response for 2.5 MeV neutrons. The total response includes a sharp peak at around 3 MeVee, corresponding to the $^{35}\text{Cl}(n, p_0)$ reaction to the ground state of ^{35}S , and a smaller peak around 2 MeVee, corresponding to the first excited state. The direct neutron response is dominant, while the back-scattered neutron contribution is minimal. Panel (b) illustrates the response functions of the 7CLYC scintillator for neutron energies ranging from 1.59 MeV to 5 MeV. Each measurement shows distinct peaks, with higher energy neutrons resulting in

Figure 3. Measurements at PTB. (a) Total, direct, and back-scattered neutron response spectra of 7CLYC for 2.5 MeV neutrons, and (b) response functions of 7CLYC for neutron energies from 1.59 MeV to 5.0 MeV. “back-scattered” refers to the shadow cone measurement and the dominant contribution will be in-scattering from the air outside the shadow cone.

Figure 4. PHS normalized by total counts at various count rates (left) and peak position stability against total count rate (right) for 2.5 MeV neutrons measured at NPL.

higher Pulse Heights (PH). The peaks shift correspondingly with the neutron energy, indicating the scintillator's effectiveness in detecting and differentiating neutron energies.

3.2 Count rate limitations

Figure 4 presents measurements conducted at the NPL with 2.5 MeV neutrons, illustrating the impact of increasing count rates on the 7CLYC scintillator's peak position stability. The left panel shows the Pulse Height Spectra (PHS), normalized by total counts, at different count rates: 140 cps, 380 cps, 1100 cps, and 1400 cps. The peak positions remain consistent across different rates up to approximately 1400 cps. The right panel plots the peak position against the total count rate, indicating stability up to about 1400 cps, beyond which a slight shift in the neutron peak position is observed. Count rate limitation is a significant factor affecting the performance of the 7CLYC scintillator, as higher rates begin to impact the accuracy of spectroscopy measurements.

Figure 5. PSD vs. PH scatter plot (left) and neutron PHS (right) for measurements at NILE with a DD generator, illustrating a prominent thermal neutron peak due to residual ^6Li and high background from scattered neutrons.

4. Application of 7CLYC at NILE with DD neutrons

Measurements acquired at the NILE facility with a DD neutron generator are presented in Figure 5, where the radiation field is significantly more complex compared to metrology laboratories due to the presence of numerous thermal and scattered neutrons. The left panel displays a PSD versus PH scatter plot, where one can already see an increased level of gamma rays and scattered neutrons. The right panel presents the neutron PHS, showing the distinct thermal neutron peak, alongside the $^{35}\text{Cl}(n,p)$ reaction peaks in both ground state and first excited state. These measurements also highlight a prominent thermal neutron peak around 3 MeVee, despite using a 7CLYC scintillator. This peak is attributed to residual ^6Li within the scintillator. Count rate limitations were addressed by positioning the detector 2.6 meters from the neutron generator within a lead shield, resulting in a count rate of approximately 1.3 kHz. This setup, however, leads to a high background of scattered neutrons, evident in the spectrum. The data underscores the challenges of maintaining peak position stability and minimizing background interference in complex neutron fields.

Figure 6 demonstrates the capability of the 7CLYC scintillator to reject the undesired thermal neutron peak using PSD. The left panel shows a zoom of the scatter plot of PSD versus PH, where a clear separation between thermal neutron and fast neutron events is visible. The diagonal cut applied in the scatter plot effectively isolates fast neutron events by leveraging the scintillator's superb PSD properties. This discrimination can happen thanks to the differentiation of protons from alpha particles among the reaction products. The right panel displays the resulting spectrum

for fast neutrons only, with the thermal neutron peak successfully removed. This separation highlights the 7CLYC scintillator's ability to produce a clean PH spectrum for fast neutrons, crucial

Figure 6. Zoom of PSD vs. PH scatter plot (left) demonstrating the discrimination of thermal neutrons using a diagonal cut, and the resulting PH spectrum for fast neutrons only (right).

for applications requiring high-resolution neutron spectroscopy and accurate neutron detection in mixed radiation fields.

5. Conclusions and outlook

The 7CLYC scintillator demonstrates superb Pulse Shape Discrimination and high-resolution neutron spectroscopy capabilities for neutrons in the 1-5 MeV range. This performance has been validated through detailed response function measurements at metrology laboratories. Furthermore, its application in the more complex radiation field of the NILE facility has shown its effectiveness in fast neutron detection, despite challenges posed by high backgrounds of scattered and thermal neutrons and limitation posed by high counting rates. A future study to avoid these limitations will see the deployment of novel scintillators containing Cl, such as LaCl_3 [7], in order to exploit the same reaction $^{35}\text{Cl}(n, p)^{35}\text{S}$ which gives a full energy peak for fast neutrons.

Acknowledgements

The results presented in this paper have been obtained in the framework of the 365 EU project RADNEXT, receiving funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, Grant Agreement no. 101008126.

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